

Impedance-based TRACT assay for SLC6A3 using HEK293 JumpIn SLC6A3 OE cells

PubChem AID: 1745858

Authors	Hubert J. Sijben ¹ , Julie J. E. van den Berg ¹ , Jeremy D. Broekhuis ¹ , Adriaan P. IJzerman ¹ & Laura H. Heitman ^{1,2}
Affiliations	¹ Division of Drug Discovery and Safety, LACDR, Leiden University, P.O. Box 9502, 2300RA Leiden, The Netherlands. ² Oncode Institute, Leiden, The Netherlands.

Assay description

The Impedance-based 'transporter activity through receptor activation (TRACT) assay detects transport activity of the dopamine transporter (DAT, SLC6A3) via GPCR-mediated changes in cell morphology. The assay is based on the principal that Co-expressed GPCR-SLC pair share a common agonist/substrate. Activation of a GPCR will result in changes in cell morphology that are detected as changes in cellular impedance using the xCELLigence RTCA system. Active SLCs transport part of the substrate into the cell leaving a lower extracellular concentration of agonist to activate the GPCR and consequently an attenuated GPCR-mediated response can be observed which reflects SLC activity (Fig. 1). Treatment with DAT inhibitors will enhance the GPCR response which is a measure of SLC inhibition. The TRACT assay can be used to determine the potency (EC_{50}) of (endogenous) G protein-coupled receptor (GPCR) agonists on JumpIn-DAT cells and enables the determination of inhibitory potency (IC_{50}) of DAT inhibitors.

Figure 1. Principal of a Impedance-based TRACT assay that relies on a shared substrate/agonist for the SLC-GPCR pair. 1) Activation of a GPCR by a agonist results in changes in cell morphology which can be detect using an xCELLigence real-time cell analyzer (RTCA) system as changes in cellular impedance. 2) Upon co-expression of a SLC, the shared substrate can be taken up by the SLC resulting in a reduced extracellular substrate/agonist concentration thereby attenuating the GPCR response. 3) Inhibition of the SLC by an inhibitor restores GPCR action to level without SLC present.

Assay protocol

Label-free whole-cell TRACT assays for the dopamine transporter (SLC6A3) were performed using the xCELLigence real-time cell analyzer (RTCA) SP system (ACEA biosciences). All assays were performed at 37°C and 5% CO₂ in 96-well E-plates in a total volume of 100 µl per well.

Cell seeding and monitoring: First baseline impedance was measured using culture medium containing doxycycline (1 µg/ml) or vehicle (milliQ water). Depending on the amount of compound additions during an experiment, background impedance at the start of each experiment was measured in 45 µl (1 addition) or 40 µl (2 additions) culture medium. HEK293-JumpIN-SLC6A3 cells were grown to 70-80% confluence in 10 cm plates prior to use in the assay. JumpIn-SLC6A3 cells were seeded at 60,000 cells/well in 50µl culture medium. The E-plate was left at room temperature for 30 min and placed in the recording station. Impedance was measured overnight every 15 min. Cells were treated 22-24 h after seeding as dox-induced protein expression is optimal after 24 h.

Cell pretreatment: Cells were pretreated with a DAT inhibitor (10 μM or increasing concentrations (100 μM – 10 μM) or a vehicle control (0.1% DMSO in PBS). Final DMSO concentration in each well was kept at 0.1%. Compounds were added in a volume of 5 μl using a VIAFLO 96 handheld electronic 96 channel pipette (INTEGRA Biosciences, Tokyo, Japan). Impedance was measured every minute for 60 min.

Cell stimulation: Cells were stimulated by the addition of dopamine or a vehicle control (1 mM ascorbic acid in PBS). Note, ascorbic acid was used in the presence of dopamine to prevent its oxidation in culture medium. Dopamine was added in a volume of 5 μl using a VIAFLO 96 handheld electronic 96 channel pipette. To determine the inhibitory potency of DAT inhibitors, cells were stimulated with a submaximal ($\text{EC}_{20} = 10\mu\text{M}$) concentration of dopamine. Impedance was measured initially every 15 seconds for 25 min, then every minute for 10 min, every 5 minutes for 50 min and finally every 15 minutes.

Data analysis: Experimental data was recorded using RTCA Software v2.0 or v2.1.1 (ACEA Biosciences). Cell index (CI) values were normalized to the first time point prior to cell stimulation to obtain normalized CI (nCI) values. Raw nCI data were exported using RTCA Software and all subsequent analyses were performed using GraphPad Prism. In all experiments, nCI values of vehicle-only conditions were subtracted from all other data points to correct for vehicle-induced, ligand-independent effects. Vehicle-corrected nCI responses were analyzed by taking the absolute net area under the curve (AUC) of the first 30 min after agonist stimulation to make concentration-effect curves. Apparent potency values of dopamine (pEC_{50}) and inhibitory potency values of DAT inhibitors (pIC_{50}) were obtained by fitting the AUC data with non-linear regression to a sigmoidal concentration-effect curve with a pseudo-Hill slope of 1 or a variable pseudo-Hill slope.

Additional information

Target data

SLC	SLC6A3
Synonyms	Dopamine transporter (DAT)
SLC sub-family	Solute Carrier Family 6 (monoamine transporter subfamily)
UniProt ID	Canonical form (Q01959)
RESOLUTE Cell ID	CE02GT-1 (HEK-SLC6A3-WTOE-p1)

Assay data

	Standard value type (i.e EC50, PoC, etc)	IC ₅₀ = 0.6 μM
	Compound name (3)	Dopamine hydrochloride
	PubChem CID	65340
	Vendor (catalogue #)	Sigma (#H8502)
	Mode of action	Substrate
	Standard value type (i.e EC50, PoC, etc)	-dox EC ₅₀ = 8 μM +dox EC ₅₀ = 46 μM

Discussion

The impedance-based TRACT assay displays a shift in EC₅₀ upon doxycycline-induction of DAT indicating that Dopamine is transported into the cell resulting in a lower extracellular concentration of Dopamine and consequently a reduced GPCR activation.

Cross references

- RESOLUTE report at [Zenodo](#).
- <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-79218-w>